

Frequency characterization of diode lasers for vapor cell clocks applications

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Abstract—The knowledge of the frequency noise spectrum of a diode laser is of interest in several high resolution experiments. Specifically, in laser-pumped vapor cell clocks, it is well established that the laser frequency noise plays a role in affecting the clock performances. It is then important to characterize the frequency noise of a diode laser, especially since such measurements are rarely found in the literature and hardly ever provided by vendors. In this paper, we describe a technique based on a frequency-to-voltage converter that transforms the laser frequency fluctuations into voltage fluctuations. In this way, it is possible to characterize the laser frequency noise power spectral density in a wide range of Fourier frequencies, as required in cell clock applications.

Index Terms—laser; frequency noise; frequency-to-voltage converter; rubidium; atomic clocks.

I. INTRODUCTION

DIODE lasers are nowadays used in a large variety of scientific and technological applications. In atomic physics, in particular, they provide the necessary narrow-linewidth optical source to study the interaction of light and atoms [1], [2]. Therefore, diode lasers have increasingly become invaluable tools in several atomic physics sectors, including frequency standards [3]–[6], laser cooling and trapping [7], magnetometry [8], and accurate gyroscopes [9], [10].

In many cases, amplitude and spectral features of the laser light are of utmost importance for obtaining the best system performances. In fact, amplitude fluctuations, usually characterized by the relative intensity noise (RIN), represent a significant limitation in any optical measurement since they directly affect the signal-to-noise ratio. Analogously, optical phase/frequency fluctuations lead to a finite linewidth value, a parameter of the laser influencing the performance of high resolution spectroscopy experiments.

In this paper, we will mainly address classes of lasers, such as distributed-Bragg-reflector (DBR) and distributed-feedback (DFB) lasers, that find application in vapor-cell frequency standards. The latter represent a promising technology for near future ground and space applications [11]–[13]. In these devices, laser frequency noise and RIN may significantly affect the clock signal. Specifically, in [14], given a laser RIN spectrum, an analytical expression is derived to evaluate its impact onto the clock Allan deviation. On the other hand, it is

recognized that laser phase noise is converted by the atomic medium into amplitude fluctuations, giving rise to an important contribution to the clock’s short-term stability [15], [16].

It is then important to estimate and characterize the magnitude of frequency and amplitude fluctuations of the diode laser used in this kind of clocks. In the paper, we will focus our analysis on frequency fluctuations mainly because the frequency noise spectral density is rarely given by laser manufacturers or found in the literature. Very often, the information about the laser frequency fluctuations is simply expressed in terms of the laser line shape and its associated linewidth. However, for vapor cell applications, this information is not always sufficient and a more complete knowledge of the Fourier distribution of the laser frequency fluctuations may be needed. The reason is that the clock servo loop requires some kind of modulation of the interrogating signal, introducing a characteristic modulation frequency (for continuously operated clocks [17], [18]) or a cycle frequency (for clocks working in pulsed operation [19]–[21]). Analogously to the Dick effect, the most relevant noise contributions impacting the clock stability are at multiples of this modulation/cycle frequency that for centimeter scale cells is typically in the range 100 Hz to 1 kHz, depending on the specific implementation. The knowledge of the laser frequency noise spectral density is then of particular relevance to elaborate a complete clock stability budget.

Various methods exist for measuring the frequency noise of a laser. One of these is the homodyne detection or delay-line method: the laser light is split into two arms and one is delayed with respect to the other before recombining both beams. The resulting response is measured with a fast Fourier transform (FFT) spectrum analyzer [22].

A variation of this technique is the self-heterodyne approach: one portion of the laser beam is sent through a long optical fiber which provides some time delay. The other portion is sent through an acousto-optic modulator. The two beams are then superimposed on a beam splitter and the frequency shifted beatnote is detected by a photodiode. This technique rejects near-DC noise and a standard RF spectrum analyzer can be used to measure the frequency noise spectrum [23]. When the time delay introduced by the delay line in the interferometer is larger than the coherence time, the mixed signals will be uncorrelated and the measured beatnote signal is not sensitive to the mean phase difference of the fields. However, for correlated fields, the observed homodyne spectrum becomes critically dependent on the optical phases [24]. It is a convenient method when only one laser source is

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available.

Another method exploits an atomic resonance as frequency discriminator, by tuning the laser frequency on the side of an optical transition [25], [26]. This technique is convenient as it does not require a reference, but it applies only to laser sources resonant with specific atomic transitions. Moreover, the slope of the frequency discriminator needs to be measured each time, as the laser detuning from resonance may vary.

In this paper we propose an alternative and robust method to measure the laser frequency spectrum based on the frequency-to-voltage (f/V) conversion. This approach is motivated by the fact that the phase noise of semiconductor laser diodes is typically too high to be characterized with high-performance commercial phase-meters, usually designed to measure low-noise RF oscillators. This technique then overcomes the limitation of the phase-meter dynamics.

In Section II we present a detailed description of the measurement scheme and a characterization of the f/V converter in terms of sensitivity and noise. In Section III, to validate the method, we measure the noise of a distributed feedback laser, in terms of its frequency noise power spectral density (PSD). The diode laser is characterized by using a narrow-linewidth frequency-doubled telecom laser, at 1560 nm, used as reference and the classical beatnote method which moves the optical laser spectrum to the RF frequency domain [27]. Conclusions are reported in Section IV.

II. OPTICAL BEATNOTE FREQUENCY-NOISE MEASUREMENT SCHEME

Figure 1 shows the measurement scheme: it foresees the generation of an optical beatnote between two lasers. Two identical diode lasers can be used or, if available, a lower-noise laser source can be used as reference. The optical-beatnote is acquired by a fast photodiode. The beatnote signal is then converted into a DC voltage using a custom-made frequency-to-voltage converter.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the measurement method. An optical beatnote between two lasers is generated and detected by a photodiode. The RF beatnote signal is converted into a DC voltage proportional to carrier frequency. In this way, an FFT spectrum analyzer (FFT SA) can be used to obtain the PSD of the laser frequency noise.

The f/V converter works with the following principle: it transforms the input RF signal into a train of pulses with fixed area and whose repetition rate is the same as the input frequency. The pulses are then smoothed out by a low pass filter, resulting in a DC voltage at the output that will be proportional to the input frequency. In more detail, the device is based on a D-latch and a NAND logic port, configured on a Complex Programmable Logic Device (CPLD). The scheme is shown in Fig. 2. The input signal is sent both to one port of the NAND and to the D-latch trigger. When a positive edge

of the input signal is detected, the output Q of the D-latch follows the D input (the latter is always forced to “high”). At this point, the NAND detects two signals above threshold at the input and sends a “zero” to the clear input of the D-latch. In this manner, the Q output is reset to “low” until the next edge is detected by the trigger. The result is a train of very short pulses, whose duration is set by the propagation time of the NAND and the Negated Clear (CLR_N) combined and whose repetition rate follows the input frequency, since each pulse is generated at each (positive) zero-crossing of the input signal. The series of pulses arrives at a low-pass-filter that averages them, producing an output voltage related to the input frequency simply by a constant multiplicative factor [28], [29].

Fig. 2. f/V converter scheme. The input is biased and sent to one input of a NAND gate and to the trigger of a D-latch (both implemented on a commercial CPLD). The Negated Preset (PRN) and the D-input of the D-latch are both forced to high. The output Q is set to high at each rising edge, and quickly reset to zero as soon as the NAND gate sends a “zero” at the Negated Clear (CLR_N) of the D-latch. The Q output is then averaged by means of a low-pass filter. The insets show the voltage signals at significant points of the circuit.

The frequency-to-voltage converter is powered by a single 5 V supply, followed by a voltage regulator, to maximize the power supply rejection ratio, and accepts sinusoidal inputs from -6 dBm to 15 dBm, with optimal performance at 13 dBm. The frequency range, by design, is 1 MHz to 200 MHz corresponding to an output voltage from 5.4 mV to 1.08 V.

In order to have precise noise measurements, the device needs a calibration. To this purpose, commercial instruments are used: a synthesizer gives a frequency sweep as input and a multimeter is employed to measure the output voltage. The analysis is repeated at different input powers to have a complete characterization of the device behavior. The calibration curve is retrieved by performing a least-square method. No appreciable difference in the calibration was found in the input power range from -6 dBm to 12 dBm, thus the device is characterized by a single sensitivity coefficient that turns out to be $a = 5.4(1)$ mV/MHz. From the calibration, the acceptable working range of f/V converter is considered in the region from 10 MHz to 150 MHz, where the deviation from a linear behavior is less than 0.1 dB [30].

Fig. 3. f/V -converter noise floor measured at different carrier frequencies. The blue line is the function expressed in eq. (2) that is used to calculate the contribution of the converter to the measured linewidth (see Table I).

To measure the device noise, a low-noise RF signal produced by a synthesizer (Agilent E8257D) is provided as input. The characterization of the f/V converter is done changing the input carrier frequency in octaves from 10 MHz to 160 MHz and the analysis is repeated for different input levels. For example, a typical measurement of voltage noise with input power equal to 12 dBm is reported in Fig. 3.

The obtained values are converted into frequency noise using the calibration coefficient previously determined and the relation:

$$S_\nu(f) = \frac{1}{\alpha^2} S_V(f) \quad (1)$$

where $S_\nu(f)$ and $S_V(f)$ are the frequency and voltage power spectral densities, respectively. The f/V noise floor is flicker, increasing with the carrier frequency, about 6 dB/oct. In the case of beatnote frequency $\nu_c = 80$ MHz, at 1 kHz the voltage noise is about -133 dB V^2/Hz , which corresponds to 32.4 dB Hz^2/Hz . No appreciable difference in the noise level was observed within the allowed input-power range.

To have a clearer picture of the type of lasers that can be effectively measured with the proposed f/V converter, we can translate the frequency-noise contribution into a contribution to the measured beatnote linewidth. To achieve this, the linewidths corresponding to the measured spectra are calculated with the β -line method [25]. Specifically, the spectra are integrated up to the a cutoff-frequency defined as the point where the PSD crosses the line expressed by the equation:

$$\beta(f) = 8 \ln 2 \frac{f}{\pi^2} \quad (2)$$

The linewidth is then taken as the square root of such integral. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
NOISE CONTRIBUTION OF THE f/V CONVERTER AT DIFFERENT CARRIER FREQUENCIES AND EQUIVALENT BEATNOTE LINewidth.

Carrier	Frequency noise at 100 Hz	Linewidth
10 MHz	24.5 dB Hz^2/Hz	370 Hz
20 MHz	29.9 dB Hz^2/Hz	795 Hz
40 MHz	36.7 dB Hz^2/Hz	1.7 kHz
80 MHz	43.4 dB Hz^2/Hz	4.3 kHz
160 MHz	48.9 dB Hz^2/Hz	10.2 kHz

Fig. 4. Beatnote frequency noise (blue) and current-driver noise contribution (red). The contributions of the f/V converter noise (black) and of the reference fiber laser (FL, green) are also reported.

III. MEASUREMENT OF A DFB LASER FREQUENCY SPECTRUM

To validate the method, we measured the frequency noise of a distributed-feedback semiconductor laser currently employed in a Rb clock experiment [19]. A fiber laser with narrower linewidth is used as reference in the beatnote scheme. The latter is a low-noise single-frequency (Koheras ADJUSTIK by NKT Photonics), co-doped Erbium/Ytterbium fiber laser at 1560 nm. It is used combined with a continuous-wave high-power fiber amplifier (Koheras Boostik). A second-harmonic generation crystal doubles the laser frequency to be resonant with the Rb D_2 line at 780 nm [31]. The DFB laser under test and the reference laser are superimposed with the same polarization on a dedicated optical bench. The detuning between the two laser is set close to 80 MHz. The beatnote signal is finally acquired by a fast photodiode, as shown in Fig. 1.

The frequency noise is measured with the fiber laser and the diode laser free-running. The measured noise spectrum has roughly a flicker-frequency slope ($1/f$) as reported in Fig. 4. The linewidth of the diode laser is measured using the β -line method and results equal to about 2 MHz, much larger than the reference, declared around 50 kHz. The f/V -converter residual noise and the fiber laser noise are also represented in Fig. 4. The latter is taken from the test report. Both contributions are at least 20 dB below the measured diode laser frequency noise. Therefore, the measurement in blue reported in Fig. 4 represents only the DFB frequency noise.

As a further characterization, we analyzed how the current driver impacts the laser performances. The driver current noise is measured independently and converted into frequency noise by means of the diode current-to-frequency sensitivity coefficient $\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial I}$. Thus, the driver noise contribution $S_{\nu, driver}(f)$ is estimated as:

$$S_{\nu, driver}(f) = \left| \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial I} \right|^2 \cdot S_I(f) \quad (3)$$

The current-to-frequency coefficient of the laser is evaluated experimentally using different sub-Doppler dips observed in a low pressure Rb cell: it results $\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial I} = 760 \frac{\text{MHz}}{\text{mA}}$. This value

is used to calculate the current driver contribution reported in Fig. 4.

From this analysis it is found that the current driver noise contribution is not negligible, limiting the performances of the diode laser, especially for Fourier frequencies above 500 Hz of the noise spectrum. In the range from 10 Hz to 500 Hz the noise induced by the current driver is about 3 dB lower than the diode laser noise. Therefore, a laser driver with a lower frequency noise contribution can be used to improve the diode laser performance and to obtain a better measurement of the intrinsic laser frequency noise.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We propose a method to measure the frequency noise spectrum close to the carrier of semiconductor diode lasers. The method relies on the acquisition of the beatnote between two laser sources, the second one being nominally identical to the laser under test or lower-noise, acting as a reference. The beatnote frequency noise is converted into voltage noise by a digital frequency-to-voltage converter and easily analyzed with FFT algorithms.

The frequency-to-voltage converter was characterized in terms of residual noise, demonstrating to be suitable for the measurements of lasers having a linewidth as low as 10 kHz.

We applied the method to measure the frequency-noise PSD of a commercial DFB laser in the spectral range from 1 Hz to 100 kHz, using a narrow-linewidth fiber laser as a reference.

This measurement setup was found to be more reliable than other schemes, such as using the side of an atomic resonance as frequency discriminator, since the conversion is determined by the instrument hardware and does not depend on environmental or laser parameters (temperature, laser power, and so on).

The setup can be expanded for measuring multiple beatnotes at once, exploiting usual cross-correlation techniques [32] once the voltage signals have been digitally acquired. In this way, an absolute characterization of the frequency-noise properties of the individual laser sources can be obtained, even in absence of a reference laser.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Elio Bertacco for his invaluable help. This work has been funded by the European Space Agency under the project GSTP Element 2 Make Industrialization of the Rb POP Clock.

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